
Are we using all of Our Rights as a Consumer?

Mutalov Dilshodjon Kadirovich, Mukhammadiyev Bakhromjon Kadirovich

Students of Jurisprudence at Namangan State University

Abstract: This article examines the rights and freedoms of our citizens as consumers, the legal measures that they can take to protect their rights when concluding a contract and in the event of its improper execution or violation of their rights.

Key words: Consumer, customer, seller, contract, benefit.

Introduction.

As a developing legal democratic country, our country has developed enough laws and regulations to protect the rights of our citizens in all aspects. Among these laws, first of all, the Civil Code, Law on Protection of Consumer Rights, Law on Metrology, Law on Certification of Products and Services, Law on Standardization, Railway Includes transportation laws. These laws are unconditionally valid in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, but nowadays our consumers do not know their rights, so they face a lot of inconvenience and violations in social life, or on the contrary, in civil courts, they are actually very simple, before the court. applications are overflowing with cases that may be resolved in the process or may not be disputed at all, which leads to a delay in the restoration of the citizen's rights, as well as to a decrease in the efficiency of work in civil courts.

The main part.

First of all, a consumer is a natural person who buys goods, orders work, services only for personal needs or for other purposes, without the goal of profit. Also, a natural or legal person who provides such goods, work or service to him is called a seller, executor. The social relationship between the seller and the buyer is contractual, and retail trade is a public offer. It is here that an important right of the consumer arises. We often see in the markets that when we want to buy some goods placed on the shop front, the seller refuses to sell the goods, saying that the goods are not for sale, that they are just put on a sample, at first glance, he is right because the goods are his, but the law does not say so. According to the Civil Code, if the seller has put the goods on display, has spread them on the shop front to show samples, or has provided informational catalogs, description photos about the goods sold at the place of sale. If this is considered a public offer, and the seller is obliged to sell the goods placed in the showcase to anyone, unless he has clearly stated that the specific goods are not intended for sale. Therefore, the consumer has the right to withdraw from the purchase of the goods purchased by him in the period he wants until he pays for them, even if the consumer has paid for the goods and no defects and defects have been found in the goods, he can simply return the goods. If he does not like the color, style, size and other reasons, the consumer has the right to demand that the product be exchanged for another within 10 days from the date of purchase, and if there is no such product, he has the right to get his money back. But there are some exceptions to this rule, and in such an exchange, it is required that the quality, shape and factory label of the goods be intact. Food products, jewelry, medicines, underwear, socks, sheets and pillowcases are not to be bought, because these types of goods lose their usefulness after one use from a sanitary and epidemic point of view. The seller must hand over the standard, valid goods to the consumer. If defects are found in the goods after

purchase, during the warranty period of the goods or during the validity period of the goods, the defective goods can be replaced, repaired free of charge and the damage paid, the contract can be canceled and the damage compensated. Also, if the warranty period and expiration date of the goods are not specified, the buyer has the right to make the above requirements for the defective goods for 2 years from the date of delivery of the goods. With the development of online markets and delivery services, many of our citizens' rights as consumers are being violated because the ordered goods or products are not exactly as described, or as shown in the picture. must exactly match the description, otherwise the buyer will have the right to return the goods, demand an exchange and recalculation, cancel the contract and pay for damages.

Another of the rights that our consumers can widely use is self-service sales, according to which the customer chooses the goods and puts them in the shopping cart. When entering such shopping centers, employees of the shopping center do not have the right to demand that the customer leave their personal belongings, bags and purses at the entrance to the shopping center, but if the customer voluntarily leaves his belongings in the designated place, the shopping store is responsible for the safekeeping of these items.

In conclusion.

As long as we live in a legal democratic state, each of us as a consumer should know our rights established by our state and demand them everywhere and at any time. we will make our contribution to the further growth and, as a result, to the effective functioning of the judicial system, to the prevention of civil disputes that often occur in our society.

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